

AR Cloud: Towards Augmented Reality at the scale of a factory

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Abstract— Augmented Reality (AR) and more generally eXtended Reality (XR) appear as one of the most promising technologies for the next decades. XR applications based on these technologies require to localize themselves in the real environment in order to register 3D virtual content in relation to the real environment surrounding the user. To achieve this, XR systems use vision sensors coupled with a SLAM algorithm to estimate their pose (position and orientation) in real-time. Unfortunately, most of existing XR systems are limited to small environments and cannot address large scale experiences. To cope with this limitation, AR Cloud technology moves in the cloud spatial computing algorithms mainly consisting in localizing the AR device while locally mapping in 3D the real environment. This 3D map is then fused with a global map shared and updated by all AR devices in order to keep up-to-date a 3D knowledge of the real world mandatory for localizing AR devices. Taking advantage of 5G bandwidth and low latency, AR Cloud is a key technology to offer shared XR experiences anywhere, at any time in real environment changing over time. We present in this paper an AR Cloud platform experimented in industry environment for displaying maintenance guidance and instructions in AR to operators.

Keywords—Augmented Reality; Spatial Computing; Cloud and Edge; Industry 4.0

I. INTRODUCTION

AR Cloud, and more generally Metaverse technologies are being announced as the next big thing for the next 10 years, with huge investment. Indeed, the AR cloud is necessary for the democratization of AR to the mass consumer market in order to provide a single AR device running anywhere at any time. Current back-end of most AR/VR headsets and autonomous agents (robots/cars/drones) implement a Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) which aim to jointly estimate the position of an agent (localization) together with a representation of the scene geometry (mapping). This is one of the fundamental problems in computer vision, and there has been tremendous progress in the last two decades. Modern approaches [1] can in real-time robustly fuse measurements coming from multiple inputs, such as cameras, odometry, depth and inertial sensors. Other methods can exploit a semantic knowledge of the scene to improve the quality of the map and thus the localization [2] [3]. However, these methods mainly focus on the reconstruction from a single device and work in relatively small-scale environments. For this reason, some multi-agent SLAM have been implemented, mainly in the

robotic domain, with the objective to share and update a common 3D map of the real environment [4][5].

AR Cloud technology consists in deploying on the edge and cloud a set of services implementing a SLAM, which provides many advantages:

- i) Most of resource-intensive spatial computing is moved from the device to the cloud, which increases the autonomy of the AR devices, improves their form-factor and their comfort (less chipsets and batteries), and reduces their price;
- ii) All AR systems share a common 3D map of the real world hosted into the cloud, without any limitations of coverage area (factory, city and more), allowing to offer AR experience anywhere at any time;
- iii) The shared 3D map is updated according to all observations captured by sensors embedded in AR devices, which keep it up-to-date over time even in high dynamic environments;
- iv) As spatial computing is executed into the cloud, it provides a unique solution compatible with any AR device to offer better interoperability for AR applications.

II. AR CLOUD PLATFORM

The AR Cloud platform has been developed using the SolAR framework [6]. Indeed, SolAR is an open-source framework under Apache V2 license allowing the creation of spatial computing pipelines dedicated to AR. Based on a C++ interface, it provides an API for more than 50 low and high level components widely used in the field of spatial computing. It also provides numerous component implementations from open-source libraries integrated in modules (e.g. OpenCV, g2o, FBoW, Ceres, OpenGV or PCL). In addition, the SolAR framework allows the development of spatial computing pipelines by assembling abstract components. Before starting the spatial computing pipelines, the instantiation and configuration of the components are performed at runtime based on a description file defining the implementation choices and configuration parameters. This provides the ability to test different implementations and component configurations without having to rebuild the pipeline. Finally, the SolAR framework provides a tool to automatically generate, for each SolAR abstract interface, a gRPC client and server. Thus, each component can call another one remotely, which provides the

communication layer to easily create services from pipelines. These services are then embedded into a docker image, and are hosted in docker repositories. Kubernetes is used to deploy spatial computing at the edge or in the cloud, the deployment is then managed with helm charts to ease the versioning, sharing, publishing and service upgrades.

Fig. 1. SolAR Framework concept: (1) Create spatial computing components from existing libraries by wrapping SolAR API; (2) Package components into modules and publish them; (3) Assemble and build spatial computing pipelines; (4) Set component implementations and configurations; (5) Create services from pipelines, embed them in docker images and publish them; (6) Deploy services at the edge or in the cloud with Helm Charts.

III. AR CLOUD SERVICES

A SLAM consists of three main components running in parallel, two related to device localization, and one to mapping. First, for localization, two distinct components are needed. The first one, called tracking, estimates the displacement of the augmented reality device at a high frequency (~60Hz). Due to error propagation, the pose of the AR device can drift over time during tracking. The second one, called relocalization, estimates the pose of the AR device at a lower frequency (~1Hz) by comparing an observation captured by the AR device with the 3D map previously built by the third component (mapping). This relocalization component is used to estimate the first pose of the AR device, when the tracking lost, and to correct the drift of the tracking.

Fig. 1. Service architecture of the AR Cloud platform.

Finally, the third component maps the real environment in 3D for future relocalizations.

Figure 2 shows the service architecture of the AR Cloud platform. The tracking is provided by existing AR runtimes (e.g., Hololens SDK, ARCore, or ARKit) and runs on the AR device due to very low latency requirements. However, the relocalization and mapping components are embedded into two distinct services and are deployed at the edge or in the cloud. An instantiation of both components is running for each AR device as a context (the map surrounding the AR device) must be preserved over time. Also, to be able to keep up-to-date a common 3D map of the real environment, a third service, called map update, hosts a shared 3D global map of the real environment and is able to update and extend it by fusing when AR session end the local map produced by each mapping service capturing changes in the real environment such as objects that have moved, been added or removed. This map update service is also able to extract a local map surrounding AR device, subpart of the global map, for each relocalization service instance in order to relocalize new AR device connected to the AR cloud platform. This local map will be routed to the corresponding mapping service instance to initialize its local map. Finally, a fourth front-end service routes input and output data between the client, the relocalization and the mapping services.

Finally, to ease the integration of the AR Cloud platform to AR applications, a Unity plugin has been developed. This plugin, supporting the Hololens SDK and the AR Foundation framework (for ARKit and ARCore), transmits the images captured by cameras embedded in the AR device and the corresponding poses estimated by the AR runtime (tracking), and receives back an offset to apply to the poses estimated by the AR runtime.

Thanks to this AR cloud platform, it is now possible to develop AR applications running continuously at the scale of a factory (~1000m²), handling simultaneously dozen of low-resources AR devices, and running over time in high dynamic environments through crowd-sourced updates of the 3D map when changes in the real environment are observed.

IV. AR MAINTENANCE USE CASE

The implemented test use case addressed AR operator guidance for maintenance work. The workflow consists of two main parts: (1) After receiving the maintenance ticket for a component in the factory or plant, the worker will be guided to the respective component's location via a directional navigation indicator in AR. (2) When standing in front of the component, AR step-by-step instructions on the maintenance procedure are displayed at spatially registered positions.

In this context the AR cloud platform provided localization information for both parts of the workflow. First an initial localization and orientation in the factory is determined. Using this information in combination with a position information on the component to be maintained (that is retrieved from a 3D model of the factory), a directional navigation information is derived and displayed in form of an AR arrow in the Hololens. The navigation arrow's orientation is then constantly updated based on the Hololens' tracking information. In order to

minimize drift errors incurred by the local tracking, periodic localization updates are provided by AR cloud platform and used for compensation of the drift.

Secondly, when the worker arrives at the target position and stands in front of the component then an update on the position and orientation information is provided by the AR cloud platform in order to correctly position the maintenance instruction holograms around the component. Again, local tracking is performed based on information provided the Hololens SDK and drift errors are compensation periodically based on the AR cloud platform’s localization information.

Fig. 2. AR Application overview

V. AR MAINTENANCE USE CASE

The AR Cloud platform has been experimented in an industrial context covering 200m². The services have been deployed on an all-in-one edge infrastructure package in a flight-case including the spatial computing server as well as the 5G RAN and Core servers, offering an autonomous solution easy to deploy in various environments (e.g., a factory or a construction site). A Microsoft Hololens 2 was used for the experimentation. It was connected to a Wi-Fi/5G gateway since the Microsoft Hololens 2 does not yet support 5G connectivity. The maintenance AR application called “Hololayer” was implemented in Unity3D and deployed on the Hololens 2 as shown in figure 3.

The experimentation was carried out in two phases. The first phase consisted in the initialization of a first mapping of the real environment. A first relocalization based on a 2D marker was used to define the reference coordinate system of the 3D map. Thus, by referencing the virtual 3D content displayed in AR in relation to this coordinate system, there is no need to additionally align the CAD models with the real world, since they are all defined in a common space. The initial map was extended to cover the entire space of 200m² by performing additional real-time captures (see Figure 4). The second phase consisted in providing the operator with contextual information in AR to achieve the maintenance task as described in the previous section. The AR Cloud platform can correctly localize the AR device in relation to the reference coordinate system of the 3D map previously created during the first phase. Thus, navigation information to reach the maintenance area as well as maintenance instruction can be

correctly registered with the real environment in AR, and this at large scale.

Fig. 3. Mapping steps. (1) Initial mapping starting on a fiducial marker; (2) Extended mapping starting from the first map; (3) map fusion resulting from the extended mapping.

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented in this paper an AR Cloud platform for offering AR applications at the scale of factory on any AR devices. By moving spatial computing services including relocalization, mapping and map update at the edge or in the cloud, the AR Cloud platform is able to maintain an up-to-date global 3D map of the real environment. This also support a crowd-sourced mode, when the 3D map is shared to multiple AR devices for allowing them to localize themselves in real-time based on observations captured by their vision sensors. The AR cloud platform has been tested in industrial environment by an AR application for navigation and maintenance tasks and we we successfully demonstrated its capacity to address large scale scenarios in real environments changing over time. We will continue the development and experimentation of the AR Cloud platform in order to optimize the localization performance and to address additional AR use cases.

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